

Dear honourable, members of the Constitution, Legal, and Parliamentary Affairs Committee:

I am forwarding my previously sent memorandum to the right email address and with a corrected attachment. My sincere apologies for this error.

Kind regards,

--

Dr. A [REDACTED] G [REDACTED], DrPH, MPH

[REDACTED]

[REDACTED]

From: G [REDACTED], A [REDACTED]
Sent: Thursday, September 30, 2021 4:43 PM
To: Daowusu-agyekun@parliament.gh <Daowusu-agyekun@parliament.gh>
Subject: Memorandum re: Promotion of Proper Human Sexual Rights and Ghanaian Family Values Bill, 2021

Dear, honourable members of the Constitution, Legal, and Parliamentary Affairs Committee:

I hope this message finds you well. Please find enclosed a memorandum in response to the Parliament of Ghana's request for written memoranda in respect to the proposed "Promotion of Proper Human Sexual Rights and Ghanaian Family Values Bill, 2021".

I am a sociomedical scientist in the field of public health with expertise in HIV prevention and care. I work at the [REDACTED] o and hold a doctorate in public health [REDACTED]. I have been conducting research in Ghana since 2011 in the LGBTQ community, particularly on the sociocultural determinants of HIV outcomes among gay, bisexual, and other men who have sex with men, a community group that the government of Ghana formerly included in its national HIV response in 2011.

The enclosed memorandum offers public health arguments in response to the proposed bill based on my work in Ghana and extant public health research.

Many thanks for your review.

Sincerely,

Dr. A [REDACTED] G [REDACTED], DrPH, MPH

[REDACTED]

[REDACTED]

MEMORANDUM

To: The Chairman and Members of the Committee on Constitutional, Legal and Parliamentary Affairs

From: Dr. A [REDACTED] O. G [REDACTED], DrPH, MPH

Re: The Promotion of Proper Human Sexual Rights and Ghanaian Family Values Bill, 2021

Date: September 30, 2021

CC: Office of the Attorney-General

1. Introduction

I am a sociomedical scientist in the field of public health with expertise in HIV prevention and care. I have a doctorate in public health from [REDACTED] and work at the University [REDACTED] as an Academic Research Specialist. My research, which has been funded by the U.S. Fulbright Program and the National Institutes of Health, primarily examines the multilevel and intersectional HIV prevention and care determinants and needs of sexual and gender minorities in Africa and in diaspora communities, including in Ghana. My active research also examines the HIV treatment needs of people living with HIV (PLHIV) in Ghana, as well as healthcare worker and health system preparedness for response to the COVID-19 pandemic. I have been conducting research in Ghana since 2011 in the LGBTQ community, particularly on the sociocultural determinants of HIV outcomes among gay, bisexual, and other men who have sex with men (MSM), a community group that the government of Ghana formerly included as a priority group in the country's national HIV response in 2011.

My work—rooted in the principles of social justice and human rights—is concerned with ensuring that all human beings, especially the most marginalized among us, are afforded the rights, dignity, and resources needed to live a full and healthy life. It is my commitment to these principles and outcomes that compel me to submit my concerns and opposition to the

proposed Promotion of Proper Human Sexual Rights and Ghanaian Family Values Bill, 2021. Below, I detail reasons to oppose the proposed Bill, informed by my expertise as a public health researcher in Ghana and by extant public health and sociological research.

2. Arguments against the Promotion of Proper Human Sexual Rights and Ghanaian Family Values Bill, 2021

a. MISINTERPRETATION AND MISUSE OF HIV DATA BY BILL AUTHORS TO JUSTIFY CRIMINALIZATION

The proposed bill claims in its Memorandum (pg. 5) that “It is our ardent belief that the passage of the Bill to deal with LGBTTTQQAAP+ is apt considering the 2017 report of the Science Research Council, communicated at the 4th National HIV and AIDS Research Conference in Accra, which indicated that 18.1% of people living with AIDS are gays (men sleeping with men).”

In addition to wrongly conflating sexual activity (men sleeping with men) with sexual orientation (how one chooses to identify their sexuality, i.e., gay, bisexual, etc.), the bill’s reference and interpretation of the cited statistic is false and suggests its authors do not understand basic public health epidemiology. This raises concerns about their use of this data and the integrity of other references in the bill to rationalize the criminalization of whole populations of people. The bio-behavioral surveillance study the bill references (Ghana AIDS Commission, 2017), a study funded by the United States PEPFAR/CDC in support of Ghana’s national HIV response, actually reports that HIV prevalence among MSM is 18.1%, not that 18.1% of PLHIV are MSM. This distinction is important. The claim in the bill would mean an estimated 63,350 MSM are living with HIV. However, based on the study report, about 4,095 MSM are estimated to be living with HIV across the eight regions surveyed out of the total number of 350,000 people living with HIV in Ghana (UNAIDS, 2020). Other government data from a 2014 mode of HIV transmission study indicates that MSM contributed 3.6% of new HIV infections; the vast majority of infections were due to heterosexual transmission (Ghana AIDS Commission, 2016).

Studies like these cited and activities within these studies, which help Ghana monitor progress in its HIV response and improve outcomes, would be rendered illegal under the proposed Bill, particularly by Sections 12, 13, 14, 15 and 16. Millions of dollars in HIV funding and by extension health programs, jobs, and activities would be jeopardized due to this bill. Moreover, the bill would reverse the years of progress made in addressing HIV in Ghana, especially among the most vulnerable populations that national HIV policies prioritize as key populations, such as MSM (Ghana AIDS Commission, 2016).

In addition to the misuse of health data, the bill's use of HIV among PLHIV as an impetus for criminalization reflects and contributes to HIV stigma—an issue that has been identified by UNAIDS and World Health Organization as one of the key barriers to HIV testing, status disclosure, and treatment (UNAIDS, 2014; World Health Organization, 2011). Intersectional HIV and anti-gay stigma are two of the biggest drivers of poor HIV outcomes globally (Alvidrez et al., 2020; S Arreola et al., 2012; Sonya Arreola et al., 2015; Jackson-Best & Edwards, 2018; C. Logie, 2019; Santos et al., 2013; UNAIDS, 2017). In Ghana, about two-thirds of people report discriminatory attitudes towards PLHIV (UNAIDS, 2019)—a statistic that reflects a failure of the country's national HIV response to educate society about HIV, its etiology, modes of transmission, effects, and treatment. Four decades into the global HIV epidemic, there is enough data demonstrating that any person can acquire HIV, that there is safe and efficacious medication available to treat people living with HIV, that with optimal engagement in treatment and care, HIV viral load can be undetected and thus untransmissible (NIAID, 2019), and that PLHIV can live long, healthy lives with adequate and quality healthcare and social support.

Finally, even if it were true that 18.1% of PLHIV were MSM, this should not justify the criminalization of gay men and other LGBTQ+ populations or any populations burdened by a health issue. The reality is that Ghana's epidemic is predominantly driven by heterosexual transmission as reported by the Ghana AIDS Commission (Ghana AIDS Commission, 2016). We cannot imagine that the authors and advocates of this bill would propose that the government criminalize heterosexuals based on this fact, yet the propose the same for LGBTQ+ people. The bill's authors are less concerned about the health of Ghanaian society

and more concerned about the repression and persecution of LGBTQ+ people—a sinister and concerning intention.

Leaders in Ghana must take a different and humane approach to discussing and addressing HIV than what this bill represents. An approach that is informed by a commitment to robust scientific evidence and to health as a human right for all people, particularly the most oppressed and marginalized LGBTQ+ people. Such an approach necessarily requires the rejection of the proposed bill and what it represents.

b. HOMOPHOBIA/CRIMINALIZATION, NOT HOMOSEXUALITY, WORSENS HEALTH OUTCOMES

As aforementioned, the proposed Bill and its authors and advocates claim that LGBTQ+ people pose health threats to the Ghanaian public. Such claims are wrong, unsubstantiated, and dangerous, and should not be considered as evidence to justify the criminalization of LGBTQ+ Ghanaians. Rather, the overall bill and specific components, like Sections 5, 12, 13, 14, 15, and 16 would lead to poor health outcomes among the LGBTQ+ people and broader Ghanaian society.

Extant public health research, including that conducted by my colleagues and I in Ghana, demonstrate that homophobic stigma, discrimination, and violence, as well as criminalization worsen health outcomes (Gyamerah, 2021; Gu et al., 2021; Gyamerah et al., 2020; Makofane et al., 2014; Meyer, 1995; Millett et al., 2012; Nelson, Wilton, Agyarko-Poku, Zhang, Aluoch, et al., 2015; Nelson, Wilton, Agyarko-Poku, Zhang, Zou, et al., 2015; Oginni et al., 2019; Santos et al., 2013; The Global Commission on HIV and the Law, 2012).

In particular, studies indicate that anti-LGBTQ+ laws worsen HIV outcomes among of LGBTQ+ people (Sonya Arreola et al., 2015; Makofane, Beck, Lubensky, et al., 2014; Santos et al., 2013; The Global Commission on HIV and the Law, 2012). A report by the MPACT (formerly known as MSMGF) also found that homophobia and internalized homophobia among young MSM was associated with lower access to HIV prevention services (Santos et al., 2013). Additionally, a 2012 systematic review examining multilevel

factors shaping HIV prevention and care among MSM globally found that, “The odds of HIV infection in Black MSM relative to general populations were nearly two times higher in African and Caribbean countries that criminalize homosexual activity than for those living in countries where homosexual behavior is legal (Millett et al., 2012).” Moreover, their analysis found that “disparities in HIV prevalence between Black MSM and general populations were two times greater in African and Caribbean countries where punishments for homosexual behavior are severe (i.e., 25 or more years in prison or the death sentence) than in those where homosexual sex is not criminalized.” In short, criminalization drives HIV rates and the passage of the proposed bill will worsen HIV outcomes among LGBTQ+ populations.

In my own research, I have documented the negative impact of anti-LGBTQ+ moral panic and backlash negatively impact the health seeking behavior of LGBTQ+ people (Gyamerah, 2021). In 2011, after the Daily Graphic, erroneously reported that 8,000 homosexuals were registered in the Western Region and that a majority was living with HIV (both false statements), the country witnessed months long media, social, and political moral panic against LGBTQ+ people, including death and arson threats, that forced peer educators and HIV prevention and care programs to go underground, as well as a reduction in clients seeking health services. Despite reporting false data, the journalists behind the publication and the figures and forces who acted on this information were not held accountable for their actions. The proposed bill, if passed, will increase the occurrence of such destabilizing and violent actions.

In 2019, while accompanying an HIV nurse to deliver medication and resources to a young MSM client who was living with HIV, I observed the degrading and inhumane treatment people living at the intersection of HIV and LGBTQ+ identity experience due to multiple intersecting stigmas. The client had been kicked out of his family home due to his HIV status and forced to live in a small shack outside the home that was located next to a gutter—living conditions that no person should endure. He did not have a place to relieve himself, was malnourished, and had defaulted from taking his antiretroviral and related treatment medication due to the impact of this stigma and treatment on his mental and physical

wellbeing. The client sadly passed away not long after the visit—an outcome that was not the result of his HIV diagnosis, but the horrendous stigma and discriminatory response by his family and community.

For every story like his, there are many more similar heart-wrenching stories that go untold in Ghana. Homophobic violence, stigma, and discrimination is driving negative health outcomes and death of members of Ghanaian society who deserve so much better.

Overall, my research in Ghana since 2011 has found that Ghanaian MSM experience and internalize multiple forms of social stressors such as violence, stigma, and discrimination that shape their HIV health seeking behavior . My analysis of data from the 2011 Ghana Men’s Study—a bio-behavioral surveillance study of MSM in four major cities (Accra/Tema, Kumasi, Cape Coast/Takoradi, and Koforidua)—found that 6.2%– 30.6% of MSM were refused services, 29.0%–48.9% experienced verbal/symbolic violence, 12.3%–30.0% experienced sexual violence, and 2.8%–12.8% experienced physical violence due to their sexuality in the preceding year (Gyamerah et al., 2020). We also found that MSM who experienced sexual violence in their first male sexual encounter were significantly more likely to not test for HIV in the preceding year in Accra/Tema and Cape Coast/Takoradi.

The table below displays additional personal excerpts on multiple forms of stigma and mental health experienced by participants in the study I was conducting during the 2019 visit, which examined the multilevel HIV treatment needs of MSM living with HIV.

Table 1. Emergent themes and related quotes from in-depth interviews with MSM living with HIV

Themes	Quotes
<i>Anti-gay stigma</i>	<i>“Society sometimes makes you feel because of your sexuality, you can’t do certain things. Like if there’s a group of boys talking in my area, I don’t go talk to them because somebody can just open his mouth and say, ‘Oh, leave here, you are a girl, you are the bitch, you’re a sissy.’ I mean, anything could just happen. So, to prevent that, I don’t want to involve myself.”</i>

<p><i>Anti-gay violence</i></p>	<p><i>“I was still looking for someone to settle down with. But the thing is the fear of approaching someone. Unless through social media. Which sometimes you really get unfortunate. Because, I have been blackmailed [as MSM] not once, but twice. In fact, beaten up, taken off my phones and other stuff, even video, being videoed naked.”</i></p>
<p><i>HIV stigma</i></p>	<p><i>“I had read so much about [HIV], so I knew it wasn’t a death sentence. But it came as a little shock to me in terms of regrets because I began—I started to regret all the things I did. I became so sad for the people that I love because I was thinking, my mom, my family, what would they think? How would they feel?”</i></p>
<p><i>Anti-gay & HIV stigma</i></p>	<p><i>“They would probably say, ‘You deserve it because you have been living the life we tell you not to live. We know you are always playing with the guys, and we told you it was wrong’ ... They wanted to stop me and I'm not stopping so [HIV] is the result of it.”</i></p>
<p><i>Healthcare stigma</i></p>	<p><i>“I met the doctor. He asked me if I have had sex, and I said, I have had sex. Then he started nagging, talking plenty, ‘We've advised you guys.’ He was asking of my background, many things; where I go to church, where I do many things.’</i></p>
<p><i>Mental health</i></p>	<p><i>“Depression is part [of it], tiredness is part [of it], wanting to end my life because one, being positive is a problem. Then two, I have to suffer to take the medication. That was stressful, you understand? Because I feel at the end of the day, you are still going to die. So why should I suffer myself and take the medication? Why don't I just quit and die?”</i></p>

Other research in Ghana have found similar issues as those documented in my research. For example, a recently published study found that a high proportion of MSM reported experiencing HIV-related stigma, same-sex behavior stigma, and gender nonconformity stigma and that MSM who perceived HIV stigma to be commonplace in their community were less likely to be linked to HIV care (Gu et al., 2021).

The proposed bill would present barriers to accessing care including anticipated and experienced stigma and discrimination at the point of care. If passed, healthcare workers

can stigmatize patients based on perceived or actual sexual and gender identities. Worse, they can report LGBTQ+ people for seeking health services that might reveal their sexual and gender identities. Such threats will prevent Ghanaians concerned about being assumed to be LGBTQ+ or outed from seeking health services. Ghana's Patients' Charter protects all people, regardless of sexual orientation and health status, from discrimination in the healthcare system. The proposed bill, especially Section 5, however would erode rights under this charter and would protect healthcare workers who refuse health services to patients due to their perceived or actual sexual and gender identities.

Passage of the proposed bill will only worsen social conditions for LGBTQ+ people and exacerbate adverse quality of life and health outcomes that exist in an already hostile society, contributing to Ghana's overall disease burden.

c. CRIMINALIATION WILL EXACERBATE STIGMA, DISCRIMINATION, AND VIOLENCE AGAINST LGBTQI+ PEOPLE, AN ALREADY MARGINALIZED GROUP

In addition to the negative health implications detailed above, the proposed bill would worsen incidents of stigma, violence, and discrimination faced by LGBTQ+ people. Despite the bill's inclusion of Section 22 (Prohibition of extra judicial treatment), the criminalization of LGBTQ+ people, including the other Sections of the Bill, are inherently violent and will embolden institutions, groups, and individuals to take actions into their own hands, especially given that the judicial system is seldom used by most Ghanaians.

Moreover, the experiences of Uganda and Nigeria after passage of their respective anti-LGBTQ+ laws offer important lessons on these consequences. Immediately following the passage of anti-LGBTQ+ laws in both countries, there were reports of beatings, vigilante violence, and even murder (Beyrer, 2014; Human Rights Watch, 2016). For example, in Uganda, the 2014 Anti-Homosexuality Act has displaced LGBTQ+ Ugandans from their country and caused a refugee crisis in neighboring country, Kenya, including the infamous Kakuma Camp (Nita Bhalla & Sally Hayden, 2018; Tony Onyulo, 2017). In Nigeria, a 2016 Human Rights Watch report described increased incidents of physical and verbal violence,

mob attacks, and killings following the passage of the Same-Sex Marriage (Prohibition) Bill (SSMPA) into law (Human Rights Watch, 2016). As the report shared, “[In Abuja] A group of approximately 50 people armed with machetes, clubs, whips, and metal wires dragged people from their homes and severely beat at least 14 men whom they suspected of being gay. Three victims told Human Rights Watch that their attackers chanted: “We are doing [President Goodluck] Jonathan’s work: cleansing the community of gays.”

These outcomes in Nigeria and Uganda reflect a global human rights crisis—that of pronounced violence against LGBTQ+ people—an issue the United Nations and other human rights organizations, including in Africa, have argued needs redress. According to a systematic review article on violence due to sexual orientation and gender identity, prevalence of physical violence among trans people ranged from 11.8% to 68.2% and sexual assault from 7.0% to 49.1% (Blondeel et al., 2018). For LGBQ people, prevalence of physical and sexual violence ranged from 5% to 34%. Trans people in particular experience high rates of violence (Park & Mykhyalshyn, 2016; Wirtz et al., 2018), increasing their risk for adverse quality of life and health outcomes (Baral et al., 2013; Brennan et al., 2012; Testa et al., 2012), such as post-traumatic stress disorder, HIV, suicide ideation, and substance use (Arayasirikul et al., 2017; Duncan & Hatzenbuehler, 2014; Gyamerah et al., 2021; Lefevor et al., 2019).

The above mentioned social stressors, such as sexuality- and gender-based criminalization and violence, impede HIV service engagement among some LGBTQ+ people and have been linked to both poor mental health outcomes such as depression, anxiety, and suicidality (Hatzenbuehler, 2009; Hatzenbuehler & Pachankis, 2016; C. H. Logie et al., 2012; Meyer, 2003; Stahlman et al., 2016). Likewise, these social stressors have been associated with poor HIV outcomes, including low testing and uptake of treatment and care (Arreola et al., 2012; Makofane, Beck, & Ayala, 2014; Millett et al., 2012; Schwartz et al., 2015).

The proposed bill will be a “recipe for violence” and exacerbate incidence of violence in Ghana as United Nations experts have argued (OHCHR, 2021) and must be rejected on these grounds as well.

d. CONVERSION THERAPY IS TORTURE AND A HEALTH HAZARD

Sections 20 and 23 of the bill proposes to institutionalize conversion therapy against LGBTQ+ people in Ghana. This proposal to institutionalize conversion therapy should raise concerns among lawmakers and health professionals. Conversion therapy is a backwards, deceptive, and pseudo-scientific practice that has been argued to be a form of torture, not therapy (IESOGI, 2020; Russell, 2020). Despite espousing to covert sexual and gender minorities to a heterosexual orientation, there is a consensus among psychological experts that conversion therapy is ineffective in doing so (American Psychiatric Association, 2018; IESOGI, 2020; Russell, 2020).

Psychological organizations like the American Psychological Association (APA) have described conversion therapy as harmful to the mental and physical health of those subjected to the treatment. In a 2013 statement, APA argued, “The American Psychiatric Association does not believe that same-sex orientation should or needs to be changed, and efforts to do so represent a significant risk of harm by subjecting individuals to forms of treatment which have not been scientifically validated and by undermining self-esteem when sexual orientation fails to change. No credible evidence exists that any mental health intervention can reliably and safely change sexual orientation; nor, from a mental health perspective does sexual orientation need to be changed (American Psychiatric Association, 2018).” Due to these documented harms, the UN Independent Expert on Protection against violence and discrimination based on sexual orientation and gender identity (IESOGI) has argued for conversion therapy to be banned globally in a recent report on the effects of this practice.

Lawmakers must reject enshrining into law a practice that is evidenced to be torturous, ineffective, and harmful. LGBTQ+ Ghanaians do not need help to “facilitate their integration into larger society” as the bill claims it will do with conversion therapy. They are already part of Ghanaian society in workplaces, communities, churches, and schools. What LGBTQ+ people need is legal protection, social support, and opportunities to work and subsist, like all other Ghanaians.

3. Recommendations and Conclusion

In summary, the proposed bill is seemingly bigotry couched in legal language with questionable, if any evidence to substantiate an attempt to politically criminalize and persecute LGBTQ+ Ghanaians. It will pose significant risks to the mental and physical health of the most vulnerable Ghanaians, their families and allies, create worse health outcomes, increase violence, and socially, politically, and economically destabilize Ghanaian society.

Rather than passing this proposed bill, it is my hope that lawmakers consider:

- 1) Decriminalizing the colonial-era Unnatural Carnal Knowledge law (Section 104 of the Criminal Code Act, 1960), which currently contributes to the negative health outcomes facing LGBTQ+ Ghanaians described in this memorandum. Ghana can take moderate steps such as researching how other countries in Africa and the Caribbean, like Botswana, Malawi and Trinidad & Tobago, decriminalized or suspended laws that criminalize homosexual acts.
- 2) Passing laws, like those in South Africa, that provide legal protections for LGBTQ+ people.
- 3) Investing in and providing socio-economic opportunities for LGBTQ+ Ghanaians to survive and thrive.

Institutionalized homophobia, including criminalization, not LGBTQ+ people, pose a threat to Ghanaian society. LGBTQ+ people have been targeted with increasing violence over the past decade; that is the crisis in need of resolution in Ghana, not the further criminalization of LGBTQ+ people in the country. It is my hope that the information I have shared can be a source of the understanding, empathy, and compassion needed to reject The Promotion of Proper Human Sexual Rights and Family Values Bill, 2021 and to take steps towards a more inclusive and safe country for all Ghanaians.

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